

Wind Farm Inertia Forecasting Accounting for Wake Losses, Control Strategies and Operational Constraints

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Introductory Summary

Future inverter-based resources (IBRs) will provide inertia emulation functionalities due to decreasing power system inertia. Wind turbines (WTs) can emulate inertia, e.g. by extracting kinetic energy reserves, but this capability depends on volatile operating conditions. Thus, the ability to forecast inertia is of interest for grid and wind farm (WF) operators. In this paper, we propose a method to forecast inertia that accounts for wake effects in a WF. The approach is based on mapping forecasted site conditions to each single WT in the WF through a wake model. The resulting inflow conditions are used to predict the WT inertial emulation capabilities, taking WT control strategies and operating limits into account.

Keywords: *Inertia monitoring and forecasting, maximum rotation strategy (MRS), kinetic energy, operating limits, power reserves, virtual synchronous machine (VSM) control*

Introduction

Power system inertia limits the rate of change of frequency (ROCOF), which is crucial for grid stability. For a high ROCOF, generation or protection units are unable to adapt the power generation or demand before violating grid frequency limits [1]. Historically, the rotating masses of synchronous machines (SMs) provided sufficient inertia. However, with decreasing generation of (directly grid-connected) SMs and increasing non-synchronous generation by IBRs, the power system inertia decreases [1]. The physical inertia of WTs is decoupled from the grid frequency for standard grid-following control. Advanced grid-following control may temporarily extract kinetic energy reserves to support the grid frequency, but the so-called ‘synthetic’ inertia cannot limit the instantaneous ROCOF [2, 3, 4]. In other words, grid-following control relies on real or so-called ‘synchronous’ inertia provided by others. New grid-forming control methods are developed to emulate ‘synchronous’ inertia by IBRs, e.g. virtual synchronous machine (VSM) control forms the grid voltage and frequency accordingly [2, 3, 4].

The approximated ROCOF $\dot{\Omega}_s = \Delta P_s / (2H_s)$ increases with decreasing power system inertia constant H_s and increasing power imbalance ΔP_s between generation and demand (with Ω_s in per unit of rated system angular velocity, ΔP_s in per unit of rated system power and H_s in s) [4]. The worst-case ROCOF events are caused by faults that split the power system into subsystems. Increasing transmission capacities, such as HVDC-links, lead to even higher future worst-case power imbalances during so-called system splits [1]. Consequently, inertia emulation of IBRs is required to limit the ROCOF and to avoid black-outs in future power systems. For instance, new German grid codes will establish a market for inertia provision by grid-forming control [5].

WT down-regulation strategies provide power reserves, which may be used for primary frequency control [6]. Moreover, down-regulation strategies may provide additional power reserves for inertia emulation [7]. This leads to contradictory requirements for maximizing the WT power generation and the power system inertia at the same time. To avoid unnecessary curtailment of renewables, grid operators need inertia forecasting to evaluate worst-case system splits and to quantify the minimum required inertia provision by IBRs. Wind farm (WF) operators will need WF inertia forecasting to offer reliable inertia provision by appropriate WT down-regulation and parameter tuning of the virtual inertia constant H_v , while taking varying wind conditions into account.

This paper considers the VSM concept to achieve grid-forming control and to provide inertia like SMs as explained in the following. For a SM, the inertia constant $H := E_{\text{kin}}/p_{\text{m,R}}$ defines its kinetic energy E_{kin} (in W s) with respect to rated machine power $p_{\text{m,R}}$ (in W) [4]. Likewise, for a VSM-controlled WT, the virtual inertia constant $H_v := E_{\text{kin,v}}/p_{\text{m,R}}$ defines the VSM kinetic energy $E_{\text{kin,v}}$ with respect to rated machine power $p_{\text{m,R}}$ of the WT. Note that $E_{\text{kin,v}}$ differs from the WT physical kinetic energy in general. In particular, a (V)SM always rotates near synchronous speed, whereas the WT speed depends on wind and operating conditions. In contrast to the WT physical inertia constant, the virtual inertia constant H_v is a tunable control parameter. Finally, aggregating all (V)SMs leads to the power system inertia $H_s := E_{\text{kin,s}}/p_{\text{s,R}}$ with $E_{\text{kin,s}}$ given by the

sum of all (V)SM kinetic energy and rated system power $p_{s,R}$ [4]. However, this is only valid for proper tuning of H_v , e.g. emulating a high H_v may be infeasible due to output power limitations.

The Electric Reliability Council of Texas (ERCOT) uses inertia monitoring and forecasting since 2016, but only for SMs based on their operating plans [8]. Alternatively, inertia monitoring based on measuring the grid frequency and the power imbalance in a (sub)system is proposed in [9, 10]. However, these approaches require additional measurement units and appropriate online power stimuli. General Electric (GE), a leading WT OEM, also proposes an inertia forecast based on machine learning using grid measurement data [9], but this is only valid for a small-signal analysis, since nonlinearities, such as inverter current saturation, cannot be taken into account.

Although a few recent publications [3, 7, 11, 4] consider inertia emulation for WTs by VSM control, how to choose the VSM inertia H_v is not discussed in detail or stated as future challenge. For instance, H_v is varied for only one operating point in [7]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, a generic approach to estimate a maximum or optimal H_v available for inertia provision is still missing. This paper thus proposes WF inertia forecasting and contributes to all necessary steps: (i) forecasting WF wind inflow conditions, (ii) predicting local WT operating points, (iii) mapping of all operating points, given by local wind inflow conditions and down-regulations setpoints, to WT inertia emulation capabilities, and (iv) aggregation of local capabilities at WF level.

Methods

A wind forecast is obtained by using a machine learning-based model. An ensemble method consisting of fully connected neural networks combines state-of-the-art numerical weather predictions (NWP) with historical measurement data, this way generating a site-specific deterministic forecast of wind speed and direction [12]. Each network is trained only on a specific segment of the overall forecast horizon, resulting in higher forecast accuracy on that segment. The final deterministic forecast is a superposition of the output of multiple ensemble networks for that segment. The wind condition forecast is given as input to a FLORIS-based WF model to accurately capture wake generation and propagation within the farm [13]. The model outputs local wind speed v_w at every WT. The predicted v_w is mapped to local WT inertia capabilities with known power setpoints based on lookup-tables (LUTs) to obtain the aggregated WF inertia emulation capability.

For each possible initial operating point $(v_w, P_{m,set,rel})$ with (local) wind speed v_w and relative power setpoint $P_{m,set,rel}$, the WT inertia emulation capability is given by

$$\forall t \geq 0 : H_{v,max} := \arg \max_{H_v} \{E_{kin,v}\}, \text{ subject to } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Omega_m(t) \geq \Omega_{m,min}, \quad M_m(t) \leq M_{m,max}, \\ P_m(t) \leq P_{m,max}, \quad \dot{M}_m(t) \leq \dot{M}_{m,max} \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

with speed limit $\Omega_{m,min}$, torque limit $M_{m,max}$, torque rate limit $\dot{M}_{m,max}$ and power limit $P_{m,max}$ (further limits may be added). The WT operating limits and grid requirements are taken into account by evaluating the WT dynamical response to a worst-case ROCOF event defined by grid codes. For each point in time t during the simulated WT response to the worst-case ROCOF, none of the constraint in Eq. (1) should be violated. In reality, WT protection schemes would fulfill all constraints but require undesired output power saturation for $H_v > H_{v,max}$.

The WT modeling and control to solve Eq. (1) includes (i) aerodynamic modeling based on power coefficient and thrust force LUTs for different v_w and tip speed ratio λ , (ii) mechanical modeling based on the drivetrain dynamic balance equation (where the additional fore-aft dynamics can be readily added), (iii) down-regulation based on a maximum rotation strategy (MRS) that maximizes the kinetic energy reserves [4, 7] and (iv) control algorithms for inertia emulation and frequency control. Moreover, control interactions have to be taken into account, e.g. the MRS should not counteract the VSM control when the WT decelerates during ROCOF events, and primary frequency control should only be activated if wind power reserves are available, see e.g. [4].

Results and Conclusions

In this short abstract we showcase the ability of the proposed method in handling turbine-level control laws and operational constraints. Figures 1a–1b show exemplary preliminary results with optimized $H_v = H_{v,max}$ at slightly below rated wind speed $v_w = 11$ m/s for different power setpoints: (i) $P_{m,set,rel} = 100\%$ in Fig. 1a and (ii) $P_{m,set,rel} = 99\%$ in Fig. 1b. In Fig. 1a, initially, the power coefficient c_p is at its maximum value and the pitch $\beta = 0$ is constant due to MPPT. The VSM inertial response increases the machine power P_m during the negative ROCOF, whereas the turbine power P_t remains almost constant. Thus, the rotor decelerates, such that the tip speed ratio λ decreases. Considering the trajectory (λ, c_p) in the upper right subplot in Fig. 1a, the

WT starts at its MPP (λ^*, c_p^*) and reaches ($\lambda_{\min}, c_{p,\min}$) at the rotor speed nadir. In Fig. 1b, due to $P_{m,\text{set,rel}} = 99\%$ the initial steady-state power quantities are 1% below the MPP values. The trajectory (λ, c_p) in the upper right subplot starts at ($\lambda_0, c_{p,0}$) and converges to the MPP (λ^*, c_p^*). Note that the controller decreases the pitch β as the WT decelerates.

Comparing Fig. 1a–1b, due to different initial WT speed, Ω_m decreases to $\min \Omega_m = 97\%$ in Fig. 1a, whereas Ω_m does not fall below its MPP-value $\min \Omega_m = 98.5\%$ in Fig. 1b. The WT deceleration leads to constant (or slightly decreasing) turbine power in Fig. 1a but increasing turbine power in Fig. 1b. Clearly, the MRS provides both additional kinetic and wind energy reserves for inertia emulation. In both cases, the machine power P_m reaches its limit $P_{m,\text{max}} = 105\%$, i.e. the power constraint in Eq. (1) is active. In this example, with solely 1% down-regulation, the MRS increases the inertia emulation capability in terms of $H_{v,\text{max}}$ by ca. 10% compared to MPPT.

Figures 1c–1d show preliminary optimization results for an operating range with active constraints marked by color in Fig. 1d. For low wind speeds, the lower rotor speed limit $\Omega_{m,\text{min}}$ is relevant. With increasing wind speed, the WT kinetic energy increases such that also $H_{v,\text{max}}$ increases. The torque rate constraint gets active before the torque limit $M_{m,\text{max}}$ and power limit $P_{m,\text{max}}$ lead to an abrupt $H_{v,\text{max}}$ reduction near rated wind speed ($v_{w,R} = 11.2\text{ m/s}$). Above rated wind speed, the power limit saturates $H_{v,\text{max}}$, but MRS down-regulation increases $H_{v,\text{max}}$ due to increasing power reserves. Below rated wind speed, the MRS increases the WT kinetic energy such that $H_{v,\text{max}}$ significantly increases with only a few percent of down-regulation.

The conference presentation will also include WF-level test cases that showcase WF inertia forecasting at an existing exemplary site in the UK. The impact due to forecast error and the dependency of WF inertia capability on inflow and operating conditions will also be discussed in detail.

Figure 1. Results: (a,b) exemplary WT response at $v_w = 11\text{ m/s}$, and (c, d) solutions of Eq. (1).

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